

Semi-Supervised Training for Biomedical Question Answering

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Abstract. The recently introduced semi-supervised method GANBERT for finetuning large language models has been applied for document relevance prediction in biomedical question answering. The additional use of unlabeled texts during training enhances the robustness of the prediction and outperforms our previous transformer ELECTROLBERT. The initial document selection phase used both for ELECTROLBERT and GANBERT has been improved using BM25 combined with RM3 query expansion with optimized parameters. Both systems were continuously improved during the BioASQ11 competition and in the last batch, GANBERT ranked as the 3rd team for document prediction. The previous version of ELECTROLBERT took the 1st place for the “yes/no” type questions in this years SYNERGY prediction.